

**AN ASSESSMENT TO UNDERSTAND THE MIASMATIC PREDOMINANCE FOR
MANAGEMENT OF CASES OF ACUTE STRESS DISORDER IN AGE GROUP OF 18 TO
40 YEARS**

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ABSTRACT

Background

Acute stress disorder (ASD) is a transient mental illness that may develop within the month following a severe experience.¹ A significant traumatic incident triggers a strong, unpleasant, and dysfunctional reaction.² Reexperiencing, avoidance, hyperarousal, and three or more dissociative symptoms are the hallmarks of this DSMV disease, which manifests two days to two weeks after the event.³

Materials and Method

The Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Hospital served as the site of the study on acute stress disorder. It was clinical research that was not randomized. Based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of 30 patients of both sexes in the 18–40 age range were chosen for the research. Following case taking, a carefully chosen treatment was recommended based on the entirety of the symptoms. The follow-up was completed one week prior to the fifth follow-up. The NATIONAL STRESSFUL EVENTS ACUTE STRESS DISORDER SCALE (NSESS) and the patients' subjective alleviation from their presenting symptoms were used to gauge recovery. The patient was requested to complete the NSESS form on the first and fifth follow-up visits.

Result

Homoeopathic treatment was administered based on the whole of symptoms. The statistical result indicates a P Value <0.001, which is regarded as statistically significant. As a result, the score before and after the acute stress disorder treatments differs significantly. Sixty percent of the patients had psora miasm, twenty-three percent had sycosis, and sixteen and sixty percent had syphilis. Prior to intervention, the mean \pm Sd score for patients with Psora was 19.78 ± 2.32 , but following intervention, it dropped to 9.56 ± 2.57 . Prior to intervention, the mean \pm Sd score for individuals with sycosis was 19.57 ± 2.07 ; it subsequently decreased to 9.43 ± 1.81 . Similarly, following treatment, the score for syphilis patients dropped from 19.00 ± 2.00 to 8.40 ± 1.95 .

Conclusion

Sixteen patients, or fifty three percent of the patients, saw significant improvement following therapy for acute stress disorder, nine patients, or thirty percent of the patients, exhibited moderate improvement, and five patients, or seventeen percent of the patients, showed modest improvement. Psora miasm was discovered to be prevalent in acute stress disorder, demonstrating the effectiveness of homeopathic remedies in treating these conditions.

Keywords

Acute stress Disorder, NSESS, stress, ASD

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM- To assess the role of miasm in management of acute stress disorder. ⁴

OBJECTIVE-

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE- To study the role of miasm in management of acute stress disorder.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVE- To study the effectiveness of homoeopathic medicines in the treatment of acute stress disorder and to review the homoeopathic literature pertaining to *Theory of chronic diseases* with respect to acute stress disorder. ⁵

BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION OF STUDY:

Depending on the type and intensity of trauma as well as the tool used to diagnose the disease, the

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prevalence of acute stress disorder (ASD) has been estimated to range from five to twenty percent. Because of disruptions in people's lives, this prevalence is rising daily. Since we have all occasionally experienced the symptoms of stress, we can all relate to people who suffer from stress illnesses. Many people with stress problems, however, experience excessive and inappropriate worry or anxiety, which significantly interferes with their daily lives and causes significant distress.⁶ Acute stress reactions, which can happen in the first month following exposure to a traumatic incident, are the hallmark of acute stress disorder.⁷

The miasmatic interpretation of ASD will be observed in this study, and the perceived stress scale will be used for analysis. Since homeopathy places an emphasis on treating the patient holistically rather than only treating symptoms, it has been shown to be an effective treatment for acute stress disorder. The person will feel better in other areas of his functioning in addition to being able to reduce stress.⁸

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design: The BHARATI VIDYAPEETH HOMOEOPATHIC HOSPITAL in KATRAJ, PUNE, was the site of the study. Individuals who met the inclusion, exclusion, and case definition criteria and complained of stress disorders were chosen. The follow-up for each of the 30 patients was conducted at the appropriate BVDUHCM OPD.

The remedies were chosen once the cases were taken. Follow-ups were conducted every seven days until the study's conclusion. Results were assessed both before and after. It was analysed statistically by a qualified statistician.

Type of study: Clinical

Allocation: Non-randomized

End result: Effectiveness

Mode of intervention: Oral route

Assessment of improvement was based on NATIONAL STRESSFUL EVENTS ACUTE STRESS DISORDER SCALE (NSESS), and subjective relief in their presenting symptoms.

On the first and fifth follow up the patient was asked to fill the NSESS form.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria:

Inclusion criteria

- Patients fulfilling the diagnostic criteria.
- Patients opting for homoeopathic treatment for their illness.
- Patients complying for regular follow up.
- Patients in age group 18-40 years of both the sexes.
- Patients who are willing to fill the consent form.

Exclusion criteria

- Patients who require emergency medical treatment.
- Patients undertaking any other mode of treatment along with homoeopathic mode of treatment.
- Pregnant and lactating females

Outcome Assessment: The patient received carefully chosen constitutional medication after a thorough case assessment. Also, follow-ups were conducted every week. Scale was used- National stressful events survey acute stress disorder short scale (NSESS) on first and fifth follow up.

RESULT

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age

Age Group	No of patients	Percentage
18-24	14	46.67%
24-30	8	26.67%
30-36	4	13.33%
above36	4	13.33%

Figure 1: Pie diagram representing Age-wise distribution of patients

Above table1 and figure 1 show that 47% of the patients had an age between 18-24 years, 27% had an age between 24-30 years, and 26.66% of patients had an age between 30-36 and 36 above in the study.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients according to Gender

Gender	Number of patients	Percentage
FEMALE	14	46.67%
MALE	16	53.33%

Figure 2: Gender-wise distribution of patients

Table no.2 and Figure 2 show that 53% of patients were males and the remaining 47% were females in the study.

Table 3: Occupation-wise distribution of patients

Occupation	No of Patients	Percentage
BUSINESS	1	3.33%
EMPLOYEE	6	20.00%
HOME-MAKER	3	10.00%
PROFESSIONAL	13	43.33%
STUDENT	7	23.33%

Figure 3: Distribution of patients according to Occupation

Table 3 and Figure 3 show the Distribution of patients according to their occupation .43.33% of patients were Professionals like architects, engineers, lawyers and MBA, 23% of patients were students, 3% of patients were in business,20% were employees and remaining 10% were homemakers.

Table 4: Distribution of patients according to MIASM

Miasm	Number of patients	Percentage
Psora	18	60.00%
Sycosis	7	23.33%
Syphilis	5	16.67%

Figure 4: Distribution of patients according to Miasm.

The distribution of miasmatic frequencies is shown in Table 4 and Figure 4. Psora miasm was present in 60% of patients, while 23.33% of the patients had sycosis, and syphilis was found in 16.67% of the patients.

Table 5: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

REMEDY	Number of patients	Percentage
ACONITE	1	3.33%
BELLADONNA	2	6.67%
BRYONIA	2	6.67%
CALCAREA CARBONICUM	2	6.67%
IGNATIA	2	6.67%
KALI- PHOSPHORICUM	3	10.00%
LYCOPodium	4	13.33%
NUX VOMICA	2	6.67%
PHOSPHORUS	6	20.00%
PULSATILLA	3	10.00%
SEPIA	1	3.33%
SILICEA	1	3.33%
SULPHUR	1	3.33%

The distribution of patients according to remedies given are shown in Table 5 and Figure 5. Phosphorus was given as a remedy to 20% of patients followed by Lycopodium which was used for 13.33% of patients. Kali- Phosphoricum was administered to 10% of patients, while Pulsatilla was used for the other 10% of patients under study.

HYPOTHESIS TESTED:

H₀: The Miasmatic approach is not effective in the management of acute stress disorder.

V_s

H₁: The Miasmatic approach is effective in the management of acute stress disorder.

Figure 5: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

Table 6: Paired t-test and Descriptive statistics of the Score before and after the intervention.

Score	N	Mean \pm SD	T Statistic Value	P-Value
before intervention	30	19.60 \pm 2.15	22.33	0.000**
after intervention	30	9.33 \pm 2.29		
95% CI for mean difference:	(9.3264, 11.2069)			

P Value <0.001, Considered to be statistically highly significant.

Hence there is a significant difference in the **score** before and after the intervention of acute stress disorder.

A test used: Paired t-test, **: Highly Significant Difference, T Statistic-value: Test Statistic value.

95% CI for mean difference: 95% Confidence Interval for mean difference

Figure 6: Bar diagram representing the Average \pm SD of the score before and after the intervention.

Table 6 and Fig 6 show descriptive Statistics and paired t-test results of the *score* before and after the intervention in the management of acute stress disorder.

Before treatment, the score was 19.60 ± 2.15 (mean \pm SD) which reduced to 9.33 ± 2.29 after treatment.

To test the hypothesis of whether the average *score* in patients, before and after the intervention of Homoeopathic medicine remains the same or not, the Paired t-test is used.

T-statistic value is 22.33 with a p-value of 0.000 ** highly significant.

We reject H_0 and conclude that there is a significant difference in average *scores* before and after the intervention in the management of acute stress disorder.

The Miasmatic approach is effective in the management of acute stress disorder.

Table 7: Distribution of patients according to improvement after intervention.

Improvement	Number of patients	Percentage
MARKED	16	53.33%
MILD	5	16.67%
MODERATE	9	30.00%

Figure 7: Distribution of patients according to the improvement after intervention.

Table 7 and Figure 7 show the distribution of patients according to improvement after intervention for acute stress disorder. 53% of patients had marked improvement after treatment, 30% of the patients showed moderate level of improvement whereas 17% showed mild improvement after treatment of acute stress disorder.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Score before and after intervention according to MIASM

Miasm	n	Mean \pm SD of the score before intervention	Mean \pm SD of Score after intervention
Psora	18	19.78 \pm 2.32	9.56 \pm 2.57
Sycosis	7	19.57 \pm 2.07	9.43 \pm 1.81
Syphilis	5	19.00 \pm 2.00	8.40 \pm 1.95

Figure 8: Descriptive Statistics of Score before and after intervention according to MIASM

Table 8 and Figure 8 describe the mean \pm Sd of score before and after the intervention according to Miasm. For patients identified with Psora, the mean \pm Sd of the score before intervention was 19.78 ± 2.32 reduced to 9.56 ± 2.57 after intervention. For patients with Sycosis the *mean* \pm *Sd* score before intervention was 19.57 ± 2.07 which reduced to 9.43 ± 1.81 . similarly for patients with Syphilis the score was 19.00 ± 2.00 which reduced to 8.40 ± 1.95 after intervention.

CONCLUSION

Following treatment of acute stress disorder, 16 patients, or 53% of the total, showed significant improvement, 9 patients, or 30% of the total, showed moderate improvement, and 5 patients, or 17% of the total, exhibited light improvement.

The patient's general state of well-being also significantly improved. Ultimately, my research demonstrated that psora miasm was prevalent in acute stress disorder and demonstrated the efficacy of homeopathic remedies in treating these conditions.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST – NIL

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AN ASSESSMENT TO UNDERSTAND THE MIASMATIC PREDOMINANCE FOR MANAGEMENT OF CASES OF ACUTE STRESS DISORDER IN AGE GROUP OF 18 TO 40 YEARS

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